

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B133
 Date: 22nd September 2005
 Project: AMPEP
 Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	----	-----
094424		INU to Nav	0.17 kft	125	
095210		start taxy	0.17 kft	125	
095956		T/O	0.82 kft	274	
100547		BBR shutter left extended ASP open	9.9 kft	334	
100701		Nevzorov zero	10.0 kft	243	
100718		J/W zero	10.0 kft	241	
103335		start descent	10.0 kft	251	
103939	105307	Run 1	0.50 kft	229	
105210		WP37	0.34 kft	201	
105441		WP48	3.6 kft	136	
105528	110644	Run 2	5.0 kft	140	
110644	111552	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.25 kft	139	
110957		interrupt P1	2.0 kft	138	
110957	111103	Run 3	2.0 kft	139	
111104		recommence P1	2.0 kft	139	
111202		interrupt P1	1.0 kft	139	
111213	111409	Run 4	1.0 kft	137	
111409		recommence P1	1.0 kft	083	
111603	111653	Run 5	0.25 kft	094	
111635		retract BBR	0.25 kft	093	
111700	111728	Profile 2	0.25 - 0.50 kft	089	
111734	113857	Run 6	0.50 kft	086	
112802		WP45	0.50 kft	084	
114013	115331	Run 7	1.5 kft	040	
114301		WP44	1.4 kft	045	
115811	121800	Run 8	1.0 kft	048	
121029		QNH 1020	0.82 kft	071	
121111		WP42	0.82 kft	064	
121800	122230	Profile 3.1	1.0 - 5.0 kft	013	
122230	122704	Profile 3.2	5.0 - 1.0 kft	012	
122416		WP41	3.3 kft	359	
122705	133948	Run 9	1.0 kft	002	
123349		QNH 1021	0.83 kft	003	
123856		WP40	0.82 kft	354	
130553		QNH 1019	0.82 kft	330	
130624		WP80	0.83 kft	323	
131436		QNH 1018	0.86 kft	317	
131900		QNH 1017	0.88 kft	316	
132225		WP79	0.89 kft	340	
133727		QNH 1015	0.92 kft	323	

133958	134130	Profile 4.1	1.0 - 0.25 kft	322
134130	134637	Profile 4.2	0.25 - 5.4 kft	337
135021	135524	Run 10	5.0 kft	170
135826	144956	Run 11	1.0 kft	150 QNH1016
140635		QNH 1017	0.92 kft	164
141756		QNH 1018	0.91 kft	144
143317		QNH 1019	0.88 kft	144
143335		WP80	0.88 kft	154
143939		QNH 1020	0.86 kft	156
151443		Land	0.24 kft	241 151443
152231		park posn. 52 04.36 N 0 37.50 W		

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B133

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date : 22-September-2005

Outline schedule:

07:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up

09:00 – Briefing

10:15 – Clear aircraft and security check

10:30 – Doors close

11:00 – Take off Cranfield

16:00 – Land Cranfield

16:30 – Debrief

18:00 – Power down

Location: A coastal transect of the South and East Coast of England

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle SSW airflow over the UK. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the South and East coasts along a coastal transect beginning in the Bristol Channel to sample background air off the coast of Cornwall. The transect of the UK outflow begins along the English Channel heading East to Dover then North to the point where airflow off the land stops, which according to current forecasts is North Yorkshire. Vertical profiles (250 – 6000 ft) once upwind in the Bristol channel and downwind of the source region off the Northumberland coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 11:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area, towards waypoint 37 in the Bristol Channel; background filter run (sampling) & NO_x calibration. Descend to 1000 ft as soon as possible into Bristol Channel, initiated over land.
- b) T+35: Cross Devon/Cornwall at 5000 ft.
- c) T+45: Descending upwind profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (2000, 500, 250)
- d) T+60: Return to 1000 ft for sampling..
Start of filter run No 1. Start of continuous bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast. 30-minute filter pack runs from here (called by Mission Scientist)

- e) T+ 200 U-turn off the Northumberland coast into wind, ascending downwind profile (250, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000).
- f) T+ 300 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 -?
3. CCM - ?
4. CCM2/Core Chemistry - Doug Anderson
5. Cloud Physics - Jamie Trembath
6. Flight Manager - Steve Devereau
7. Mission Scientist - Eiko Nemitz
8. Bag Sampling 1 - Chiara di Marco
9. Bag Sampling 2 - Alison Perry
10. Filters/CCN - Stuart Heath
11. AMS - Hugh Coe
12. ptrms - Anne Hulse
13. WAS - Jim Hopkins ?

- Transit to Bristol Channel
- descend to point 37 50:55N 4:50W
- 48 50:50N 4:40W
- 46 50:01N 3:25W
- 45 50:01N 2:00W
- 44 50:40N 1:00W
- 43 50:40N 0:30E
- 42 51:05N 1:30E
- 41 51:53N 1:47E
- 40 52:41N 1:47E
- 87 53:00N 1:00E
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 77 55:45N 1:30W
- 79 50:00N 1:10W
- 80 54:05N 0:05E
- 87 53:00N 1:00E
- Cranfield

Init : Tue,20SEP2005 06Z Valid: Wed,21SEP2005 12Z

10m Wind (kt)

Daten: GFS-Modell des amerikanischen Wetterdienstes
(C) Wetterzentrale
www.wetterzentrale.de

CO (g/m3) 22/09/05

Forecast of CO concentration based on Unified Model meteorology from 20/09/05.

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at 1000ft.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: N/A

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO, NO_{xy}(HNO₃)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.133**

Date 22/09/2005

Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:00	T/O				broken cloud to base 2000 - 3200 ft + high level cirrus
10:15		FL100		52.07/1.46	heading for somewhat denser cloud towards SW band of broken cloud following extension of Bristol Channel
					NOx appears to be working
					* clear profiles of CO ₂ & NO ₂ indicating well mixed & capped BL up to 1000 m
10:23					more cloud except for along river & Bristol Channel.
10:24					late start of Fitts Peak transit run due to misinterpretation of FS runs; continue run through Bristol Channel
10:32					leaving FL100, initially for 4000 ft. through to 500
10:39	R1	@ 500 ft			only downward facing beams received
10:42					wind 3 kts @ 140° or 13 kts @ 163° Bristol channel: hazy but no cloud, horizon poorly defined. ~ 3 ppt of NOx
10:45					changing to forward facing receiving
10:49					wind 5 kts @ 176° or 16 knots @ 170°
10:52					WP 37
10:53	R1				end of run; end of transit Fitts run
10:54					2500 - 3000 ft some cloud over land
10:55	R2	FL50			
11:02					cloud cover extends over English Channel but clouds become less convective
					wind at 500 ft 7 kts @ 143 or 17 @ 205

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.133**.....

 Date 22/09/2005.....

 Page 2 of 4.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:06	P1	5000 ft			interrupted → 250 ft
11:10	R3	2000 ft		1 min	
11:12	R4	1000 ft			
					thin level cloud foggy @ 1000 ft
11:15	R5	250 ft			more NOx was ground, CO ₂ less clear
11:22					wind 4 m/s @ 176° or 10 knots @ 184°
11:27					visibility improving somewhat, horizon just visible
11:27					wind @ WP 45 1 m/s any direction
11:33					visibility down again, wind 3 m/s @ 180°
11:39	R5	end	at	800 ft	forced to climb by low cloud
11:40	R6	@ 1500 ft			; CO drops & PCTSP & ATCS NO ₃ ⁻
11:43		WP 44			↳ end of filter run 1
11:44					wind 3 m/s @ 263°
11:50					all cones rising white still at 1500 ft
11:53	FP2	start	of	run	
11:53	R7	end	of	run (19 ans before WP 43)	@ 1500
					trying out visibility at 1000 (poor) & 500 (poor)
					returning to 1000
11:58	R8	@ 1000 ft			winds 4 m/s @ 203°
12:04					wind 5 m/s 198° fine but land
12:07					bad over sea, still heavy
12:10					wind 3 m/s @ 199° ATCS NO ₃ ⁻ > 10 µg m ⁻³
12:11					WP 42
12:18	R8	end	start	of profile P2	1000 → 5000 ft

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....133.....

Date22/09/2005.....

 Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:21		clear			mission horizon
12:24		WP 41			
	P3	profile down			small emission @ 1300 ft
12:27	R9				
12:32		wind			7 m/s @ 153° or 8 kts @ 189°
12:36		wind			increased to 7 m/s @ 157° or 10 kts @ 189°
12:43	FP3	start			past PT40 (should start seeing outflow)
		visibility			improving slightly; PARS falling
12:48		WP 87			
12:52		picking up			outflow; wind 6 m/s @ 169°; 17 kts @ 214°
12:59		wind			9 m/s @ 180° or 20 kts @ 193°
13:06		WP 80			
13:07		wind			9 m/s @ 182° visibility improving PARS falling
13:12		narrow			CO plume
13:14		horizon			clearly visible
13:20		clear			outflow plume; large H ₂ O and H ₂ /SO ₂ ratio low CO!
13:29		too wind			10 m/s @ 182° or 22 kts @ 192°
13:32		narrow			plume
13:35		end of			FP3 run
13:36		WP 77			
13:39		end of			run 9
		continuous			profile to 5300, falling to 5000 to stay clear of cloud.
13:48	R10	@ 5000 ft			in precipitation

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B133

Date: 22/09/05

Operator:JT

Page1 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
				Not requested	Not requested			Not requested			SID not requested
											2D imaging probes not requested
											DAU 1 17 seconds slow
10:39:39	1570	0.09	8								Start run 1 500ft
10:41:00	13231	0.09	8								
10:43:00	1440	0.09	8								
10:45:00	1529	0.09	8								
10:47:00	1787	0.09	8								
10:49:00	1623	0.09	8								
10:51:00	1697	0.09	8								
10:53:07	1776	0.09	8								End of run 1 – run 2 missed
11:06:43	71	0.09	8								Start of P1 descent 5000ft
11:07:52	571	0.09	8								4000ft
11:08:49	1982	0.1	8								3000ft
11:09:57	1827	0.09	8								2000ft interrupt P1 start run 3
11:10:58	1544	0.09	8								End of run 2 restart P1 2000ft
11:12:01	1826	0.09	8								1000ft interrupt P1 start run 4
11:14:09	1904	0.09	8								End run 4 restart P1 1000ft
11:15:52	2269	0.09	8								End P1 250ft start run 5
11:16:52	2136	0.09	8								End of run 5 Start P2 250ft
11:17:28	1541	0.09	8								End P2 start run 6 500ft
11:19:00	1718	0.09	8								
11:21:00	2741	0.09	8								
11:23:00	2780	0.09	8								
11:25:00	1905	0.09	8								
11:27:00	2982	0.09	8								
11:29:00	4046	0.09	8								
11:31:00	4611	0.09	8								
11:33:00	3761	0.09	8								
11:35:00	3628	0.09	8								
11:37:00	3079	0.09	8								
11:38:55	2879	0.09	8								End of run 6

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

Page 2 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:40:13	1114	0.08	8								Start of run 7 1500ft
11:42:00	1198	0.09	8								
11:44:00	1275	0.09	8								
11:46:00	929	0.09	8								
11:48:00	750	0.09	8								
11:50:00	2644	0.09	8								
11:52:00	2929	0.09	8								
11:53:31	2162	0.09	8								End of run 7
11:58:11	2390	0.09	8								Start run 8 1000ft
12:00:00	2691	0.09	8								
12:02:00	3446	0.08	8								
12:04:00	2910	0.09	8								
12:06:00	3388	0.09	8								
12:08:00	4039	0.09	8								
12:10:00	3045	0.09	8								
12:12:00	2969	0.08	8								
12:14:00	6000	0.09	8								
12:16:00	5605	0.09	8								
12:18:01	4627	0.1	8								Start P3.1 1000ft end run 8
12:19:16	3302	0.09	8								2000ft
12:20:17	1949	0.09	8								3000ft
12:21:19	24	0.09	8								4000ft
12:22:30	7.79	0.06	8								5000ft end P3.1 start P3.2
12:23:28	101	0.06	8								4000ft
12:24:31	3193	0.09	8								3000ft
12:25:45	4369	0.1	8								2000ft
12:27:04	5099	0.09	8								1000ft end P3.2 Start run 9
12:29:00	5103	0.09	8								
12:31:00	4949	0.1	8								
12:33:00	4642	0.1	8								
12:35:00	4579	0.1	8								
12:37:00	4992	0.1	8								

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B133

Date:23/09/05

Operator:JT

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:39:00	4758	0.1	8								
12:41:00	4134	0.1	8								
12:43:00	3716	0.09	8								
12:45:00	3067	0.09	8								
12:47:00	2564	0.09	8								
12:49:00	3629	0.09	8								
12:51:00	3185	0.09	8								
12:53:00	3384	0.09	8								
12:55:00	3826	0.09	8								
12:57:00	4650	0.09	8								
12:59:00	3737	0.09	8								
13:01:00	3415	0.1	8								
13:03:00	2986	0.09	8								
13:05:00	2189	0.09	8								
13:07:00	1203	0.09	8								
13:09:00	1048	0.08	8								
13:11:00	890	0.08	8								
13:13:00	785	0.09	8								
13:15:00	572	0.09	8								
13:17:00	691	0.09	8								
13:19:00	381	0.08	8								
13:21:00	516	0.08	8								
13:23:00	897	0.08	8								
13:25:00	925	0.08	8								
13:27:00	1025	0.09	8								
13:29:00	905	0.08	8								
13:31:00	619	0.08	8								
13:33:00	588	0.08	8								
13:35:00	719	0.08	8								
13:37:00	811	0.08	8								
13:39:00	683	0.08	8								
13:39:45	564	0.09	8								END RUN 9

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:39:48	649	0.08	8								Start P4.1 1000ft to 250ft
13:41:30	686	0.09	8								500 end P4.1 start P4.2
13:42:36	583	0.09	8								1000
13:43:16	467	0.09	8								2000
13:44:11	507	0.1	8								3000
13:45:07	69	0.21	8								4000
13:46:07	2.98	0.06	8								5000
13:46:30	15.5	0.06	8								5400ft end P4.2
13:47:00											5000ft run 10
13:53:00	135	0.08	8								
13:55:28	151	0.08	8								End run 10
13:58:26	962	0.08	8								Start run 11 1000ft
14:00:00	658	0.08	8								
14:02:00	688	0.08	8								
14:04:00	842	0.08	8								
14:06:00	783	0.08	8								
14:08:00	796	0.08	8								
14:10:00	658	0.09	8								
14:12:00	603	0.08	8								
14:14:00	1041	0.08	8								
14:16:00	700	0.09	8								
14:18:00	562	0.09	8								
14:20:00	484	0.08	8								
14:22:00	602	0.09	8								
14:24:00	581	0.09	8								
14:28:00	697	0.09	8								
14:30:00	1766	0.09	8								
14:32:00	2933	0.09	8								
14:34:00	3164	0.1	8								
14:36:00	3318	0.1	8								
14:38:00	3585	0.1	8								
14:40:00	4071	0.1	8								

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B133

Date:

22nd Sept 2005

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet TEFLON/NYLON/PAPER	Bottom inlet TEFLON / PAPER
-----------------------------------	-------------------------------------	------------------------------------

Run No	Disk No 1	Disk No 2	Disk No 3	Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
	TOP	MIDDLE	BOTTOM						
Transit	50	51	161	Top	10.24Z	10.53Z		450	
Transit	116	183	154	Bottom	10.24Z	10.53Z		907	
Filters run1	126	111	5	Top	11.19Z	11.42Z		434	
Filters run1	159	142	92	Bottom	11.19Z	11.42Z		977	159 FILTER PAPER LOOSE
2	141	85	18	Top	11.53Z	12.17Z		412	
2	123	89	56	Bottom	11.53Z	12.17Z		1067	123 FILTER PAPER LOOSE
3	158	131	23	Top	12.43Z	13.36Z		966	
3	121	113	155	Bottom	12.43Z	13.36Z		1947	
4	98	114	10	Top	13.59Z	14.29Z		548	
4	143	87	93	Bottom	13.59Z	14.29Z		1016	
5	152	86	13	Top	14.33Z	14.50Z		324	
5	134	124	135	Bottom	14.33Z	14.50Z		639	134 FILTER PAPER LOOSE
6 Transit	133	89	58	Top	14.55Z	15.05Z			
6 Transit	140	101	145	Bottom	14.55Z	15.05Z			
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					
				Top					
				Bottom					

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS	
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5		
101125	101155	100 FL	20.95	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.02	0.50	0.75	1.13	1.45	2.12	S Background.
			21.04	286	432	465	466	809	D
			21.12	275	267	271	277	286	B
			20.99	2321	2316	2343	2386	2416	R
				965.5	965.2	965.3	965.3	965.3	P
103000	103036	100FL	21.39	0.50	0.74	1.11			S Descend
			21.31	277	374	511			D
			21.29	289	289	287			B
				2412	2397	2387			R
				965.5	965.5	965.7			P
104006	104039	500ft	21.38	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.40	0.50	0.74	1.10	1.44	2.09	S
			21.69	812	1366	1770	2466	2694	D
			21.61	354	348	343	343	377	B
			21.61	2317	2315	2307	2305	2301	R
			21.22	1006.2	1006.5	1006.1	1006.3	1006.2	P
104740	104810	500ft	21.41	0.50	0.73	1.11	1.45	2.11	S
			21.39	965.	1390	2323	2916	2071	D
			21.85	353	349	349	352	388	B
			21.78	2305	2302	2298	2302	2305	R
			21.72	1006.2	1006.2	1006.0	1006.5	1006.9	P
111237	111308	1000ft	21.	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
				0.50	0.72	1.13			S
				2006	2244				D Descend
				369	369				B
				2325	2332				R
				1006.1	1006.3	100.			P
111825	111850	500ft	21.79	0.49	0.73	1.09	1.42	2.09	S
			22.40	2502	3176	3767	4034	4092	D
			22.10	306	312	378	365	367	B
			22.31	2571	2418	2428	2431	2438	R
			22.15	1006.5	1006.6	1006.4	1006.4	1006.5	P
112548	112618	500ft	21.83	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			21.83	0.49	0.73	1.09	1.42	2.10	S
			22.38	3224	3041	3495	3952	4001	D
			22.35	407	405	423	421	425	B
			22.31	2447	2445	2444	2444	2439	R
				1006.3	1007.9	1007.2	1007.1	1007.7	P
113305	113340	500ft	22.14	0.50	0.73	1.09	1.44	2.09	S
			22.52	2195	3012	3891	3994	4024	D
			22.49	275	376	274	371	375	B
			22.61	2438	2432	2428	2422	2420	R
				1007.6	1007.4	1007.1	1007.2	1007.1	P

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS	
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5		
114558	114628	1500ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.59	0.51	0.14	1.09	1.42	2.09		S
		22.58	2560	2579	3426	3795	4592		D
		22.54	335	340	376	349	335		B
		22.40	2412	2436	2444	2448	2450		R
		22.25	1006.4	1006.3	1006.3	1006.2	1006.1		P
115825	115859	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.84	0.48	0.74	1.09	1.42	2.06		S
		22.81	2917	3298	3819	4002	4092		D
		22.70	376	381	376	380	382		B
		22.27	2448	2451	2442	2432	2430		R
		22.31	1006.3	1006.3	1006.4	1006.4	1006.3		P
120615	120645	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.15	0.49	0.72	1.05	1.41	2.11		S
		22.11	3812	3909	4092	4092	4092		D
		22.28	494	461	467	470	471		B
		22.18	2429	2476	2407	2405	2407		R
		22.21	1006.4	1006.3	1006.3	1006.9	1006.9		P
123025	123101	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.37	0.49	0.76	1.12	1.42	2.09		S
		22.26	4092	4092	4092	4092	4092		D
		22.31	647	641	635	639	641		B
		22.35	2343	2353	2379	2426	2440		R
			1006.7	1006.8	1007.0	1007.1	1007.1		P
125030	125102	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.29	0.49	0.75	1.09	1.44	2.05		S
		22.23	3968	4092	4092	4092	4092		D
		22.69	482	468	471	478	482		B
		22.64	2408	2391	2389	2380	2372		R
		22.61	1007.6	1007.6	1007.7	1007.7	1007.7		P
130535	130602	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.69	0.49	0.74	1.10	1.46	2.11		S
		22.05	2959	2998	3865	4092	4092		D
		22.09	505	520	521	535	522		B
		22.15	2281	2278	2272	2271	22		R
		22.09	1006.6	1006.7	1006.7	1006.6	1006.7		P
131726	131747	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.29	0.50	0.73	1.10	1.44	2.11		S
		21.78	3042	3854	3965	4092	4092		D
		21.81	443	451	455	460	452		B
		21.88	2276	2308	2340	2379	2396		R
		21.89	1006.7	1006.1	1006.4	1006.2	1006.2		P
131930	131902	1000ft		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.29	0.48	0.74	1.12	1.43	2.07		S
		22.23	2291	2388	3901	4092	4092		D
		22.40	421	429	451	429	424		B
		22.43	2401	2399	2394	2390	2386		R
		22.43	1004.8	1004.7	1004.7	1004.6	1004.6		P

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5	
135845	135910	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.73	0.48	0.73	1.08	1.40	2.04	S
		23.03	13.76	15.22	21.95	22.23	4092	D
		23.17	334	341	348	340	342	B
		23.07	2336	2329	2324	2318	2312	R
		22.11	1003.5	1003.5	1003.4	1003.4	1003.4	P
140600	140631	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		22.76	0.50	0.72	1.10	1.42	2.07	S
		22.77	14.63	22.12	22.95	27.60	4046	D
		23.02	314	332	331	328	325	B
		22.94	2308	2301	2297	2292	2288	R
		22.91	1004.1	1004.2	1004.1	1004.1	1004.1	P
141720	141749	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.21	0.49	0.73	1.09	1.41	2.06	S
		23.18	1653	1686	2350	4092	4091	D
		22.19	320	324	328	330	480	B
		23.18	2283	2279	2277	2276	22	R
		23.16	1005.3	1005.3	1005.3	1005.5	1005.3	P
142700	142732	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.07	0.49	0.72	1.08	1.42	2.03	S
		22.99	2102	1901	2488	2905	4092	D
		23.07	329	332	335	340	342	B
		23.05	2291	2295	2298	2302	2302	R
		23.10	1005.4	1005.5	1005.4	1005.3	1005.4	P
143520	143552	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.21	0.50	0.71	1.08	1.39	2.04	S
		23.26	2093	2738	3295	4092	4091	D
		23.38	509	517	520	519	525	B
		23.48	2395	2332	2344	2340	2338	R
		23.45	1006.2	1006.0	1006.1	1006.5	1006.6	P
144300	144331	1000ft	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
		23.27	0.49	0.73	1.07	1.42		S
		23.40	2371	3265	3891	4092		D
		23.48	582	587	590	589		B
		23.59	2396	2364	2367	2371		R
			1006.6	1006.6	1006.7	1006.7		P
			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
								S
								D
								B
								R
								P
								S
								D
								B
								R
								P

end run
and climbed.

Flight No. B133 Route

Date 22/09/05 Take Off 11:00

Bag Samplers: CHIARA, STEVE

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
304	10:13:45	+30"			
170	14:45	+30	59		
192	17:45	+30	52 02 15 N	01 43 26 W	
251	20:45	+30			
143	23:45	+30	51 53 85	02 23 33 W	
486	26:45	+30			
163	29:45	+30	51 45 86	03 04 78 W	
168	32:45	+30			
463	35:45	+30	51 34 77	03 42 01 W	
073	38:45	+30			
190	41:45	+30	51 20 80	04 07 48 W	
022	44:45	+30	51 14 00 N	04 19 56 W	
258	47:45	+30	51 06 70 N	04 31 86 W	
321	50:45	+30	50 59 21 N	04 43 63 W	END RUN 1 @ 10 53 07 500M
213	53:45	+30			
217	56:45	+30	50 44 11	04 30 43 W	RUN 2 @ 10 55 28 150M
345	59:45	+30			
361	11:02:45	+30	50 27 66	04 04 50 W	
147	11:05:45	+30			
334	11:06:45	+30			① 11 06 44 P6H1
188	07:45	+30	50 18 73 N	3 43 90 W	
196	08:45	+30			
331	09:45	+30	50 08 31	3 31 85	
400	10:45	+30			
384	11:45	+30			① 11 20 2 RUN 4
097	12:45	+30			
283	13:45	+30	50 00 36 N	3 19 55 W	
171	14:45	+30			
515	15:45	+30			① 11 5 52 RS
427	16:45	+30			
521	17:45	+30			① 11 17 28 RG
530	18:45	+30	50 01 50	2 52 36	
194	19:45	+30			
279	20:45	+30			
119	21:45	+30			
556	22:45	+30	50 01 11	2 29 01	
358	23:45	+30			
448	24:45	+30			
239	25:45	+30	50 00 88	0 21 21 W	
160	26:45	+30			
434	27:45	+30			

Flight No. B133 Route

Date 22 SEP 05 Take Off 1000 Z

Bag Samplers: CHIMERA STN

Sheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
110	11:28:45	+30'			
507	29:45	+30			
364	30:45	+30			
187	31:45	+30	50104.1N	0145.26W	
008	32:45	+30			
126	33:45	+30			
343	34:45	+30			
091	35:45	+30	5020.8J	0129.40W	
607	36:45	+30			
394	37:45	+30			
233	38:45	+30			
009	39:45	+30	5030.4J	114.00W	1500' 114013 R7
063	40:45	+30			
101	41:45	+30			
496	42:45	+30			PT44
285	43:45	+30	5039.9J	056.18W	
374	44:45	+30			
379	45:45	+30			
282	46:45	+30			
013	47:45	+30	5040.1J	034.0PW	
261	48:45	+30			
658	49:45	+30			
382	50:45	+30			
162	51:45	+30			
650	52:45	+30			
338	53:45	+30	5040.10	003.26	
078	54:45	+30			
403	55:45	+30			
048	56:45	+30			PT43
132	57:45	+30			1000' R8 (T) 115211
473	58:45	+30	5044.7P	028.28(E)	
335	59:45	+30			
435	12:00:45	+30			
230	01:45	+30			
611	02:45	+30	505		
323	03:45	+30	5056.5JN	050.10E	
177	04:45	+30			
088	05:45	+30			
327	06:45	+30			
388	07:45	+30	5100.4IN	0112.45E	
489	08:45	+30			

Flight No. R133 Route

Date 22 SEP 05 Take Off 1000 ~~z~~

Bag Samplers: CHIARA STEVE

Sheet No. 3

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
339	12:09:45	+30			
470	10:45	+30			PT 42
140	11:45	+30			
349	12:45	+30	5110.28N	0132.35E	
082	13:45	+30			
087	14:45	+30			
452	15:45	+30			
164	16:41	+30	5124.96N	0137.15E	
086	17:45	+30			
265	18:45	+30			
040	19:45	+30			
053	20:45	+30	5140.41N	0142.65E	
066	21:45	+30			
532	22:45	+30			
464	23:45	+30			
387	24:45	+30			
478	25:45	+30			
328	26:45	+30	5205.10N	0147.65E	1000' R9 (D) 12.27.05
025	27:45	+30			
030	28:45	+30			
651	29:41	+30			
454	30:45	+30	5221.50N	14810E	
189	31:45	+30			
601	32:41	+30			
425	33:45	+30			
488	34:45	+30	5234.9N	0149.2E	
205	35:45	+30			
218	36:45	+30			
014	37:45	+30			
215	38:41	+30	5248.4	0149.9E	PT 40
332	39:41	+30			
058	40:45	+30			
451	41:41	+30			
060	42:45	+30	5256.3N	0130.5E	
028	43:45	+30			
271	44:41	+30			
381	45:41	+30			
186	46:41	+30	5304.1	0106.8E	
288	47:41	+30			PT 87
392	48:41	+30			
314	49:41	+30			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
220	12:50:45	+30			
249	12:51:45	+30	5315.9	046.8E	
005	12:52:45	+30			
042	12:53:45	+30			
460	12:54:45	+30			
522	12:55:45	+30	5330.7	034.20E	
084	56:45	+30			
322	57:45	+30			
255	58:45	+30			
145	59:45	+30			
011	13:00:00	+30	5347.6	019.7E	
172	02:00	+30			
180	03:00	+30			
499	04:00	+30			
043	05:00	+30			
121	06:00	+30	5403.8	001.8E	PT 80
074	07:00	+30			
252	08:00	+30			
047	09:00	+30			
226	10:00	+30			
280	11:00	+30			
029	12:00	+30	5421.3	018.6W	
091	13:00	+30			
391	14:00	+30			
526	15:00	+30			
354	16:00	+30			
237	17:00	+30	5436.9	041.1W	
625	18:00	+30			
209	19:00	+30			
173	20:00	+30			
089	21:00	+30			PT 75
106	22:00	+30			
442	23:00	+30			
055	24:00	+30			
002	25:00	+30			
152	26:00	+30	5504.6	0108.0W	
612	27:00	+30			
007	28:00	+30			
243	29:00	+30			
236	30:00	+30	5520.0N	0117.3W	
211	31:00	+30			

Flight No. B133 Route

Date 22 SEP 05 Take Off 1000 Z

Bag Samplers: CHIARA STANE

Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
411	13:32:00	+30			
484	13:33:00	+30			
487	34:00	+30	5533.6N	0129.9W	
136	35:00	+30			
017	36:00	+30			ADM PT 77 ↑
158	37:00	+30			
057	38:00	+30			
093	39:00	+30	5549.1	0150.3W	
600	40:00	+30			
080	41:00	+30			
026	42:00	+30			
050	43:00	+30			
622	44:00	+30	5604.9	209.4W	
268	45:00	+30			
399	46:00	+30			
127	47:00	+30			
396	48:00	+30			
503	49:00	+30	5614.4	202.4W	
245	50:00	+30			
402	51:00	+30			
052	52:00	+30			
246	53:00	+30			
206	54:00	+30			
084	55:00	+30			
018	56:00	+30	5534.7	0141.2W	
083	57:00	+30			
524	58:00	+30			1000' R11 (T) 135826
256	59:00	+30			PT 77 ↓
123	14:00:00	+30			
311	14:01:00	+30			
185	02:00	+30	5537.6	0125.7W	
485	03:00	+30			
223	04:00	+30			
061	05:00	+30			
505	06:00	+30	5522.7	0117.4W	
393	07:00	+30			
551	08:00	+30			
051	09:00	+30			
510	10:00	+30	5511.8N	0111.00W	
421	11:00	+30			
056	12:00	+30			

Flight No. B133 Route

Date 22 SEP05 Take Off 1000Z

Bag Samplers: CHILERA STAVE

Sheet No. 6

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
128	14:13:00	+30			
385	14:00	+30	5457.1	0103.7W	
290	15:00	+30			
250	16:00	+30			PT 79
178	17:00	+30			
254	18:00	+30			
104	19:00	+30	5443.6	050.16W	
096	20:00	+30			
064	21:00	+30			
102	22:00	+30			
242	23:00	+30			
100	24:00	+30	5428.7	028.4W	
031	25:00	+30			
071	26:00	+30			
528	27:00	+30			
424	28:00	+30			
184	29:00	+30			
095	30:00	+30	5414.6W	007.7W	
619	31:00	+30			
458	32:00	+30			
157	33:00	+30			PT 80
035	34:00	+30			
062	35:00	+30	5400.6	0008.9E	
543	36:00	+30			
130	37:00	+30			
617	38:00	+30			
032	39:00	+30			
621	40:00	+30	5345.7	0021.8E	
003	41:00	+30			
012	42:00	+30			
058	43:00	+30			
511	44:00	+30			
133	45:00	+30	5330.5N	031.1E	
115	46:00	+30			
615	47:00	+30			
107	48:00	+30			
618	49:00	+30			
626	50:00	+30	5312.5	0031.8E	END RUN 11 (T)44956
310	51:00	+30			
610	52:00	+30			
517	53:00	+30			

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/9/05

FLIGHT:

OPERATOR: H COE

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	Y		
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	Y		
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	Y		
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	Y		
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	Y		
	Turn on: Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	Y		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	Y		
	Turn on Alcatel... 100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	Y	Monitor Pump Currents	@07:20 BST ALL 100% 5 TOOK S LIGHTLY LONGER THAN REST BUT CURRENTS ALCO.
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box			
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box			
	Turbo pump 6 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box			
Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	Y			
Turn on heater	Electronics box	Y	Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	08:00 BST 23	
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	Y		08:44 BST
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	Y	Approx 125Hz	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	Y		
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	Y		
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	Y	NEGATIVE NUMBER	
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	Y	now 2.075	
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	Y		
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	Y		
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	Y	COMPLETE @	08:50 BST

EV 0.93A
0.865
BST

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/9/05

FLIGHT: 133

OPERATOR: H COE

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		BACK TO 2.575
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	N/A		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		OK L (a) next time
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	F=1.977 AB 34x10 ⁶
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	CHESON
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	S=4.1 D=350 a=0.7
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓	CONNECTED O PARTICLE FILTER	
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMS\AMSCODE\AMSMENU.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓			
Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓		ZERO PARTICLES AS O PR FILTER	
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o				

IFP NO 520
N4, 590

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE:

FLIGHT:

OPERATOR:

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS,Grimm CPC logging	Software	Y	STOPPED CPC	
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	Y	NOT STOPPED AMS	BUT ON ZERO PF
	Exit Labview		Y		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	Y		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	Y		
	Open Inlet		Y		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu,Averaging and saving tab	Y		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	Y		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	Y	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	Y	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	Y	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	Y		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	Y		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	Y	Check tof windows	MS CAL
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit		SMPS s=4.1,a=0.41,350nm	AS.
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		P		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	ONE	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	OR		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	FLIGHT		
	General alteration,10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	↓	Check tof windows	
	Close inlet				
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop				
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
	Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
ShutDown	Turn off Multiplier & Balzers	Electronics box			
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box			
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack			
	Turn off heater,chopper,the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers			

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/9/05 FLIGHT: B133

OPERATOR: *HC*

Tuning

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	18	16	22
Def Outer	9	8	11
Heater Bias	-5.87	-5.69	-6.5
Focus	11.75	12.25	12.5
Extraction	134	42	220

TIME: 16:30	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.45	n/a
KV Change	2.45kV	0.025kV
Gain	1.92x10⁶	3.00E+06
G used Change		1

OLD

TIME: 16:30	New	Typical
KV	2.5	n/a
KV Change	0.075	0.025kV
Gain	2.55x10 ⁶	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.88	1

PRE FLIGHT

*TIME LOCAL 16:30
2.55
0.05
3.02x10⁶
1.18*

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.24x10 ⁻⁶	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.914	4
IPP NO3	520	400
IPP NH4	571	550
Airbeam MS	2.79x10 ⁶	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.83x10 ⁶	2.00E+06
Run Number	09:12:09	n/a

TIME: <i>T1</i>	New	Typical
IE (NO3)		2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)		4
IPP NO3		400
IPP NH4		550
Airbeam MS		2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF		2.00E+06
Run Number		n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	0:10 - 0:282
Run number	9891 - 9892

TIME:	
Run number	

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 22/9/05 FLIGHT: B133

OPERATOR: M OAE

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.28	0.86	99	98
2	3.4	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.62	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

11:36Z

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.28	0.86	99	98
2	3.4	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.62	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

12:40Z

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.28	0.86	99	98
2	3.4	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.62	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Time

14:00Z

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.28	0.86	99.4	98
2	3.38	3.5	100	100
3	1.35	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.62	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 133

Date: 22 September 2005

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		n
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		n
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope		N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2		N
Heimann		N	HVPS		N
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25		N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100		N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		n			
FWVS		N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC		N
Upper Clear		Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red		Y	CVI		n
“ Silicon		Y			
“ JO1D		Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear		Y	PSAP		N
“ Red		Y	Nephelometer		N
“ Silicon		Y	Filters		Y
“ JO1D		Y	AMS		Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES		N	NIR TDLAS		N
SWS		N	2BT O3		N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC		N
Ozone		Y	PEROXIDE		N
SO2		Y	Formaldehyde		N
NOX		Y	ADA		N
CO		Y	CPI		N
ORAC		N	NOxy		N
PAN		n	PTRMS		N
PERCA		N	Bag Sampling		Y
WAS		n	Tube Sampling		N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B133

Date: 22 September 2005

Instruments

- 1 TWC not fitted
- 2 Unable to load tapes on outboard video recorder

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B133:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Eiko Nemitz
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

4 x Forward / Downward Facing Cameras